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Energy data analytics visual tool

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List of abbreviations

Acronym	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CSV	Comma Separated Values
SQL	Structured Query Language
UI	User Interface
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
RDBMS	Relational DataBase Management System
UUID	Universally Unique IDentifier
API	Application Programming Interface

Executive Summary

The document outlines the development of an innovative AI Visual tool within the DATA CELLAR ecosystem, with a primary focus on enhancing data analytics capabilities in the energy sector. This tool is designed to empower energy data analysts to create, deploy, and share machine learning models, facilitating the extraction of valuable insights from energy datasets.

The development environment will prioritize the user experience as a pivotal component, relying predominantly on a user-centric visual approach. This approach empowers even those without extensive expertise to effortlessly construct and execute a data analysis pipeline. This is achieved through the integration of pre-loaded building blocks, including algorithmic and data blocks.

To this end, Orange Data Mining software was chosen from among the available open-source solutions to serve as the basis for the AI visual tool. Its capability to facilitate the seamless design and configuration of advanced data analysis workflows through the simple drag-and-drop of pre-built blocks played a crucial role in the selection process.

This deliverable comprises three key sections. It begins with a comprehensive exploration of the Orange Data Mining tool, highlighting the rationale behind its selection as the foundation for the AI Visual tool in Section 2. Subsequently, the document delves into the development process, with a specific focus on the creation and functioning of training and inference pipelines in Section 3. Finally, section 4 elucidates the server-side architecture, emphasizing the deployment of AI services initially developed locally. Finally in section 5 a list of possible improvements and next steps to be taken are provided.

The visual tool represents a significant leap in democratizing data analysis, fostering collaboration, and promoting data-driven decision-making within the energy sector. Its technical capabilities promise to drive innovation and sustainability in the energy industry while catering to the evolving needs of DATA CELLAR stakeholders.

1. Introduction

In the context of the DATA CELLAR data space, the utilization of energy data is crucial. Energy data analysts play a vital role in deciphering complex datasets to extract valuable insights that can enhance efficiency, sustainability, and innovation in the energy sector. To facilitate this process, user-friendly tools need to be implemented to enable users to create and share machine learning models.

The main objective of this endeavour is to establish a versatile platform that empowers energy data analysts to design, develop, and seamlessly deploy new and advanced algorithms and models for extracting insights from energy datasets shared within the data space. When effectively harnessed, these insights can drive informed decision-making, optimize resource allocation, and promote innovation in the energy sector. Ultimately, the task aims to facilitate the continuous enhancement of analytical capabilities among participants in the data space.

The goal is to create an ecosystem where energy analysts can easily incorporate new libraries into their analytical toolkit, enabling the swift integration of cutting-edge techniques and methods into their workflows, and sharing these tools with other platform users.

A notable feature of this data analytics visual tool is its commitment to user experience, this development prioritizes accessibility, focusing on a user-centric, visual approach. Our approach empowers both data analysis experts and non-experts, offering a powerful yet intuitive interface for creating and executing data analysis pipelines.

The development process actively builds upon open-source solutions, with a strong emphasis on Orange Data Mining, a versatile and powerful platform that serves as the cornerstone for providing users with a robust and user-friendly interface for constructing data analytics pipelines. This platform enables users to design and configure sophisticated data analysis workflows with ease.

The choice of opting for Orange Data Mining over alternative open-source solutions is driven by its inherent alignment with the essential requirements for our visual tool. Orange facilitates the construction of machine learning pipelines by leveraging pre-built building blocks, streamlining the development process. However, a significant challenge arises as Orange is designed as local software, lacking a built-in mechanism for deploying models onto servers. To overcome this limitation, a necessary step involved reverse engineering Orange and customizing it to seamlessly incorporate the capability of deploying models on a server, thereby addressing this critical gap.

These constructed data analytics pipelines will be seamlessly uploaded to a central server through web APIs. This server will facilitate the deployment and accessibility of these models for other users within the DATA CELLAR ecosystem, allowing for collaborative data analysis and knowledge sharing, as well as enabling the creation of energy data economy through the marketplace and DATA CELLAR's incentivisation scheme.

In the following chapters a comprehensive and in-depth explanation of the prototype AI visual analytics tool will be provided.

2. Orange data mining

2.1. Overview

As already mentioned, the software used to provide the basic UI functionalities is Orange [1][2]. Orange is a powerful open-source data mining and machine learning software tool that has gained popularity for its accessibility and versatility. It was developed by researchers at the University of Ljubljana in Slovenia and is constantly evolving with a vibrant community of contributors. The heart of Orange's appeal lies in its user-friendly, visual programming interface, which makes it an excellent choice for users with varying levels of expertise, from beginners to experienced data scientists.

Orange is built using Python, a widely used programming language in the field of data science and machine learning. It leverages various Python libraries and frameworks, such as NumPy [3] for numerical operations and scikit-learn [4] for machine learning algorithms. This allows users to seamlessly integrate their Python code and custom scripts into Orange's workflow, enhancing its flexibility and extensibility.

The software offers a rich set of components for data preprocessing, including tools for data cleaning, transformation, and feature selection. It also provides a plethora of data visualization options, allowing users to gain insights into their datasets quickly. Orange's visual interface is based on a modular, drag-and-drop paradigm, where users can connect data sources, processing components, and modeling algorithms to create comprehensive data analysis pipelines, it is possible to see an example of Orange user interface in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1 Example of Orange User interface [5], on the left there is the widget list, each widget can be used by simply drag & dropping it on the right part and connect it to other widget to create a workflow

In terms of machine learning, Orange supports a wide range of algorithms for classification, regression, clustering, and more. It simplifies the process of building and evaluating models, making it easy to compare different algorithms and approaches. Orange also incorporates feature-rich widgets for model evaluation, including various performance metrics, cross-validation, and data splitting methods.

Orange's flexibility extends to its ability to handle various data types, including numerical, categorical, and text data. It can handle complex data integration tasks, including data fusion and data augmentation, which are essential in real-world data analysis scenarios.

Additionally, Orange's vibrant community has contributed to its vast library of add-ons and extensions, allowing users to expand its functionality to suit their specific needs. These extensions cover a broad spectrum of domains, including bioinformatics, image analysis, and text mining.

Moreover, the Orange Data Mining community offers a vibrant ecosystem of support and learning materials [6], making it an invaluable resource for both newcomers and experienced users. Within this community, users can access extensive documentation, tutorials, and educational resources that cover a wide array of topics, from introductory guides to advanced techniques. Additionally, a passionate and collaborative community of users and experts provides support through forums, discussions, and Q&A platforms, where individuals can seek assistance, share insights, and find solutions to their data analysis challenges. This rich repository of knowledge and the supportive network of Orange users make learning and mastering data mining more accessible and enjoyable.

In summary, Orange is a versatile and user-friendly data mining and machine learning tool, built on Python and enriched with a wide range of components and capabilities. Its visual interface empowers users to work with data efficiently and effectively, and its extensible nature allows for customization and expansion, making it an invaluable tool for data analysis and modeling across various domains.

2.2. Widgets

Widgets are the building blocks of Orange platform, serving as fundamental components that empower users to create and customize their data analytics workflows. These widgets are specialized tools that perform various data-related tasks, from data preprocessing and visualization to modeling and evaluation. They can be seamlessly connected and arranged within the user interface to design complex data analysis pipelines.

With a diverse library of widgets at their disposal, users can choose the specific widgets that best suit their analysis needs, making it a highly flexible and adaptable tool. Each widget provides a straightforward and intuitive interface, making it accessible for users with varying levels of expertise in data mining. This modular and visual approach to data analysis, supported by an extensive library of widgets, grants users the flexibility to construct tailored workflows, unlock valuable insights, and make data-driven decisions with ease. Orange Data Mining widgets are the backbone of this user-friendly and powerful platform, enabling users to unlock the full potential of their data. In Figure 2-2 a list of the main widgets available in Orange is presented. The widgets are grouped in different categories depending on the functionality they offer.

Figure 2-2 List of available widgets in Orange split by category

Here's a list of some of the main widgets in Orange, divided by category:

Data: This category encompasses widgets related to data loading and saving.

- Data Table: Displays attribute-value data in a spreadsheet
- File: Reads data from a file
- CSV File import: reads data from a CSV File
- SQL Table: reads data from a SQL database

Transform: this category includes widgets that help users modify and enhance the dataset's structure, improving data quality and relevance for analysis:

- Data sampler: Creates a new dataset by resampling the existing dataset
- Merge: Merges two or more datasets into a single dataset

- Select Columns: Selects a subset of features from a dataset
- Select Rows: Filters data based on specified conditions

Visualize: this category provides widgets that allow to create graphical representations of data, aiding in the exploration and understanding of data patterns

- Line Chart: Creates a line chart of a dataset
- Scatter Plot: Creates a scatter plot of a dataset
- Histogram: Creates a histogram of a dataset
- Box Plot: Creates a box plot of a dataset

Model: these widgets enable users to create, train, and evaluate various machine learning models for tasks like classification, regression, clustering, and more

- Linear Regression: Predicts a continuous target variable using a linear model
- Logistic Regression: Predicts binary outcomes using a logistic model
- Support Vector Machines: Classifies data points by finding an optimal hyperplane
- Decision Tree: Classifies data points using a tree-like structure of decisions
- Random Forest: Classifies data points with an ensemble of decision trees

Unsupervised:

- K-Means: Clusters data into K groups based on similarity
- Hierarchical Clustering: Creates a hierarchy of data clusters
- PCA: Reduces dataset dimensions while preserving information

Evaluate: The Evaluate category contains widgets that assist in assessing the performance of machine learning models, providing insights into model accuracy and reliability.

- Evaluation Results: This widget allows the user to assess the performance of his models and provides insights into their accuracy and reliability
- ROC Analysis: The ROC Analysis widget is used to evaluate classification models using ROC curves and related metrics, helping you assess the model's predictive power

Time Series: Time Series widgets offer specialized tools for the analysis and forecasting of time-dependent data, critical for tasks involving temporal patterns and trends.

- **Plot Time Series:** Creates a plot of a time series dataset
- **Moving Average:** Computes the average of data points in a moving window
- **ARIMA:** is a time series forecasting model that combines autoregressive, differencing and moving average components to capture past patterns, remove trends and seasonality, and make predictions based on historical data

Explain: these widgets help users understand and interpret the results of their models, enhancing transparency and accountability.

Fairness: Fairness widgets address fairness and bias concerns in machine learning models, promoting equitable predictions.

Finally, Orange allows users to develop their own widgets [7] by writing Python code to extend the functionality of the software. This process involves defining input and output ports for the widget, specifying its behaviour and appearance, and integrating it into the Orange canvas. With this approach, users can tailor Orange to their specific needs, add new data preprocessing or analysis functionalities, and create custom visualizations, making the tool a powerful platform for data mining and analysis.

3. Pipeline definition

3.1. Orange as the data analytics visual tool

In the previous chapter, it was discussed how Orange possesses the majority of the required characteristics for the AI Visual tool. Its primary limitation, however, lies in its distribution method as it is currently available only as downloadable software for local use. This limitation prevents it from natively supporting pipeline sharing and deployment as a web service, which are crucial steps for enabling the user of DATA CELLAR to access the models created by other users.

Our primary focus has been addressing this gap, enabling users to train a model locally while also developing a pipeline that enables its utilization for inference. This pipeline can then be uploaded to a server and deployed, ultimately providing access to other users in the data space.

The upcoming sections of this chapter will delve into the process of developing the model before its upload, while in Chapter 4 the overall server architecture and model deployment will be explained.

3.2. Training pipeline

The initial stage in the model development process involves the creation of a training pipeline. This pipeline is essentially a sequence of interconnected widgets, where each widget serves a specific function. Starting from an initial set of input data, the pipeline systematically processes the information, one widget at a time, until it reaches the final widget, which yields the desired output.

The purpose of this training pipeline is to generate a trained model as its ultimate output. This trained model can then be saved for future use within other pipelines, offering the flexibility to apply the knowledge gained from one model to various data analysis and prediction tasks. This approach not only streamlines the development process but also promotes reusability and efficiency in the utilization of trained models for a wide array of applications.

An example of training pipeline can be seen in Figure 3-1.

Designing a pipeline is inherently a creative process, and it doesn't adhere to strict rules regarding the mandatory inclusion of specific widgets. The suitability of widgets in a pipeline depends on several factors, such as the unique characteristics of the data at hand, its abundance, the desired output, and the developer's skillset.

While a comprehensive discussion on how to create an effective machine learning model is beyond the scope of this document, as it's a vast and continuously evolving subject, there exist some general guidelines that can serve as a foundation for developing a theoretically sound model in Orange.

Figure 3-1 Example of training pipeline, The pipeline loads, preprocesses, and splits the dataset. A Random Forest model is trained, evaluated, and visualized using the predict widget. The "Save model" widget stores the model in pickle (.pkcls) format..

1. **Dataset Import:** Start by importing the dataset into Orange. One can load data from various sources, including CSV files, databases, and web services. Orange's user-friendly interface makes it easy to visualize and explore your data.
2. **Data Preprocessing:** Data cleaning and preparation. This may involve handling missing values, normalizing or standardizing features, encoding categorical variables and identify the most relevant features for the model. Orange provides a wide range of widgets to assist in data preprocessing tasks.
3. **Train-Test Split:** It involves partitioning the available data into two distinct sets: a training set used to train the model and a testing set used to evaluate the model's performance. The train-test split is essential for assessing how well the model generalizes to unseen data, helping to avoid overfitting, which occurs when the model performs well on the training data but poorly on new, unseen data. Properly managing this split is vital for ensuring the reliability and effectiveness of the machine learning model in practice.
4. **Model Selection:** Select the machine learning algorithm one want to use for training the model. Orange supports a variety of algorithms, including decision trees, support vector machines, and neural networks.
5. **Model Training:** Configuration and training of the selected model using the training dataset. In this phase it is needed to experiment with different parameters and settings to optimize model performance.

6. **Evaluation:** Consist in assessing the model's performance using various evaluation metrics like accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score. Orange provides widgets for model evaluation and visualization of results.
7. **Tuning and Optimization:** Fine-tuning of the model by adjusting hyperparameters and conducting feature engineering if needed. The results of the evaluation needs to be taken into account to guide these adjustments.
Moreover, to ensure the model generalizes well, it is generally useful to perform cross-validation to estimate its performance on unseen data. Orange simplifies this process with dedicated widgets.
8. **Final Model Export:** Once one is satisfied with the trained model, it is possible to export it for future use or deployment. Orange allows one to save models in pickle format using the “*Save model*” widget, this is a fundamental step as the exported model will be used in the inference pipeline as explained in the next paragraph.
The pickle format is a widely used method for serializing and deserializing Python objects. Serialization involves converting complex data structures, such as lists, dictionaries, and custom Python objects, into a byte stream, which can be easily stored or transmitted. Deserialization is the reverse process of reconstructing the original Python objects from the byte stream. Pickle is a module in Python that facilitates this process.

In summary, training an Orange model involves a well-defined sequence of steps, from data import and preprocessing to model selection, training, evaluation, and ultimately the creation of a reusable pipeline. With the flexibility to adapt to specific data and needs, Orange provides a user-friendly platform to effectively harness the power of machine learning, enhancing data analysis and predictive modeling.

3.3. Inference pipeline

After successfully training and saving a machine learning model, the subsequent critical step is the development of the inference pipeline. This pivotal process in Orange entails creating a well-organized process for the application of the trained model to unseen data, with the primary goal of making accurate predictions or classifications. An example of inference pipeline can be seen in Figure 3-2.

Figure 3-2 Example of inference pipeline, on the left the inference dataset is loaded as a as a placeholder. Then data is preprocessed consistently with training, the saved model is applied to the input, finally data is saved using the "Save Data" widget.

The definition of the inference pipeline follows a more straightforward process as it is meant to replicate the same process as the training pipeline without the operations needed for the training itself; here’s a list of the needed steps:

1. **Load Inference Dataset:** Begin by loading the inference dataset, typically a placeholder for new, unseen data that will enter the pipeline. As will be explained in the next chapter, this step must be performed by the “Load CSV” widget because it functions as the anchor point to inject data coming from API’s requests into the pipeline.
2. **Data Preprocessing:** After loading the data, it must be ensured that it undergoes preprocessing in a manner consistent with the preprocessing applied during the training pipeline. This consistency is crucial to maintain the same data standards, transformations and format.
3. **Load Trained Model:** The centerpiece of the inference pipeline is the trained model saved during the training process. This model must be loaded to apply it to the preprocessed input data. The model

has learned patterns and relationships from the training data and is now ready to make predictions or classifications.

4. **Model Application:** the loaded model is applied to the preprocessed input data, which may involve tasks such as generating predictions, classifying data, or providing insights based on the model's training. The model's application is the core of the inference process, enabling it to generalize to new data.
5. **Save or Export Results:** Once the model has processed the new data, the results can be saved or exported using the "Save Data" widget. As for the "Load CSV" widget, the "Save data" widget is required for enabling the server side components to retrieve the output of the deployed models, so it must be included.

Once the inference pipeline is ready, it needs to be saved in the orange XML format (.ows). The saved models, represented as (.pckls), are crucial components of the AI service. To enable the deployment of the AI service, these files must be uploaded to the server, where they will be stored and activated upon request.

4. Pipeline deployment

4.1. Architecture

Until this point, all the tasks have been executed "user-side" using a local installation of the Orange Data Mining software. This process resulted in the generation of an inference pipeline file and a pickle file containing essential information about the trained model's weights. The combination of these two components forms the foundation of our AI service. To facilitate the publication and the accessibility of these AI services, we designed and developed a backend architecture, as illustrated in Figure 4-1. This architecture serves as the backbone for making our AI capabilities available to a broader audience.

Figure 4-1 The AI Visual tool's server architecture, centered on a main Docker container, uses Web APIs for model upload and inference. A modified Orange version interprets .ows files, injecting data into the pipeline. Azure Blob storage stores files, and a PostgreSQL database manages model metadata.

At its core, the architecture is built around a Docker container, which serves as the main module. This container is responsible for exposing a set of Web APIs, which are instrumental in the seamless upload of machine learning models and their subsequent application for inference. These Web APIs form the interface through which users can interact with the system.

Within this server-side architecture, the key to the successful execution of inference lies in a modified, headless version of the Orange data mining tool. This tailored version of Orange has been specifically adapted to accommodate the parsing of uploaded .ows files, which are Orange workflow files. When a user uploads an .ows file, the container leverages this headless Orange instance to inject the necessary inference data into the workflow, which mirrors the processes followed during model training. The uploaded data is processed within the pipeline and the output is then extracted.

The central Docker container is well-supported by additional components. An Azure Blob storage system plays a pivotal role in the architecture, serving as a repository for both .ows and .pkcls files. These files are copied to the file system to deploy the pipeline when an inference is requested.

Furthermore, the server-side architecture integrates a PostgreSQL database, which functions as a robust metadata repository. This database stores vital information related to the uploaded model to enhance the overall management and organization of the models, allowing for efficient tracking and retrieval of model-related information.

4.2. Headless Orange parser

Central to the server-side architecture is the headless version of the Orange data mining tool. In this context, "headless" denotes that it operates without a graphical user interface, focusing solely on data processing and modeling functionalities. This specialized iteration of Orange has been adapted to accommodate the parsing of uploaded .ows files, which are XML-based Orange workflow files. These .ows files adhere to a structured XML format, enabling them to encapsulate detailed information about the data transformations and model configurations employed during the model training phase.

By adjusting the server version of Orange, we enable the ability to utilize the built-in parser without the need for a graphical user interface or any form of user interaction. This modification is crucial in achieving an exact recreation of the workflow, mirroring the local execution precisely. This meticulous replication is essential to establish and maintain a high level of consistency between the local pipeline and the server-based pipeline.

One Obstacle we had to overcome was adapting the inference pipeline for use in a client-server environment. The obstacle revolved around seamlessly integrating new data, which originates from user requests, into the pipeline. Locally, these pipelines were initially designed to work with static files. Similarly, output data also needed a way to be extracted from the pipeline and delivered to the user. To address these issues, we implemented modifications to the parsing process. This involves injecting the new data into the "Load CSV" widget and extracting the results from the "Save data" widget, this is the reason why these two widgets are required in the inference pipeline.

This relatively straightforward adjustment allowed us to repurpose the inference pipeline, which was originally designed for local use, into a service that could operate effectively in a client-server architecture. This adaptation is a crucial step in making the AI Visual tool accessible to a wider audience and enabling remote, on-demand model inference.

When a user uploads an .ows file, the Docker container leverages this headless Orange instance to inject the requisite inference data into the workflow, aligning it with the processes followed during model training. This synchronization ensures that the newly uploaded data adheres to the same standards and transformations applied during the initial model development. As a result, this uploaded data traverses through the pipeline, following a sequence of interconnected nodes, each representing a specific data transformation or modeling step. Finally, the output is meticulously extracted and made available for user access or further actions.

It's important to highlight that for the inference pipeline to function correctly, it necessitates the presence of a "Load Model" widget. Furthermore, it's crucial that the model name configured within this widget precisely matches the name of the uploaded model as a pickle file. This requirement is essential because, in theory, multiple models can be used within the same inference pipeline. To maintain clarity and ensure the

right “Load Model” widget is associated with the appropriate .pkcls file, it's imperative that the names correspond accurately. This alignment enables the system to effectively connect the "Load Model" widgets with their corresponding .pkcls files, facilitating seamless model integration in the inference pipeline.

The headless version of Orange plays a pivotal role in orchestrating the intelligence behind the AI Visual tool, harmonizing the inference process with the intricate processes established during model training, thus enabling the seamless execution of AI services.

4.3. Docker

Docker [8] is a widely used containerization platform that streamlines software development and deployment. It accomplishes this by encapsulating applications and their dependencies within self-contained, lightweight containers. These containers are highly efficient, thanks to their ability to share the host operating system's kernel, reducing resource consumption and enabling rapid startup.

Applications are packaged in Docker images, which serve as templates for containers. These images can be custom-built or obtained from Docker Hub, a repository of public images.

Containers are living instances of Docker images, offering a consistent, controlled environment that ensures uniform behavior across different computing environments. Persistent storage is provided through data volumes, ensuring data integrity across container restarts and facilitating data sharing between containers.

Docker's networking capabilities enable seamless communication between containers and external systems. Custom networks can be created, containers connected to specific network segments, and container ports exposed to the host or external networks.

Docker has become an industry standard due to its efficiency, portability, and user-friendliness, allowing developers to create, test, and deploy applications consistently across diverse computing environments.

Docker was chosen to containerize both the headless version of Orange and the FastAPI endpoints to ensure consistent and isolated environments. It simplifies deployment, enhances portability, and manages dependencies, making it easier to scale and maintain the system across various platforms and environments. This approach streamlines the process of reproducing the exact conditions required for executing the headless Orange version and FastAPI endpoints, ensuring consistent and reliable performance.

4.4. PostgreSQL

PostgreSQL [9] is an open-source RDBMS renowned for its robustness and extensibility. PostgreSQL ensures compatibility with SQL and supports various programming languages. With a strong emphasis on extensibility, it allows users to define their data types, operators, and even functions, making it a versatile choice for a wide range of applications. It also implements advanced concurrency control mechanisms and provides features like multi-version concurrency control (MVCC), making it an excellent choice for applications with high transaction loads.

PostgreSQL's scalability and comprehensive feature set make it a reliable and flexible database solution for both small-scale projects and large enterprise applications.

PostgreSQL was selected to store model metadata due to its robust and versatile nature as a relational database management system. Its relational structure enables efficient organization and retrieval of complex data, making it an ideal choice for storing detailed information about the trained models. This ensures that metadata, such as model versions, configurations, and performance metrics, can be structured and queried effectively, supporting model management and tracking. Furthermore, PostgreSQL's relational database capabilities make it well-suited for accommodating additional data models and standards, like the DATA CELLAR data model and GAIA-X compliance (i.e. storing verifiable credentials).

4.5. Azure Blob Storage

Azure Blob Storage [10] stands as a pivotal component within Microsoft's Azure cloud platform, providing scalable and cost-effective object storage for a myriad of applications. As a fundamental service, it facilitates the secure and efficient storage of massive amounts of unstructured data, ranging from text and images to videos and binary data.

One of the key advantages of Azure Blob Storage is its inherent scalability. It seamlessly accommodates the varying storage needs of applications, allowing users to scale up or down based on demand. This elasticity, coupled with the ability to store and access data from anywhere globally, makes it an ideal solution for enterprises with diverse and geographically dispersed workloads.

Azure Blob Storage robust encryption mechanisms, access controls, and Azure Active Directory integration ensure that data remains protected at all levels. Additionally, features like Azure Storage Firewalls and Virtual Networks enhance the security posture, making it a trusted choice for businesses with data protection requirements.

Azure Blob Storage also easily integrates with other Azure services, enabling users to build comprehensive solutions for data analytics, backup, and disaster recovery. Its versatility extends to support for various data access tiers, allowing users to optimize costs by aligning storage performance with their specific application requirements.

In conclusion Azure Blob Storage allows organizations to efficiently manage and leverage vast volumes of unstructured data in a secure, scalable, and flexible manner, making it an integral part of Microsoft's cloud ecosystem for modern data storage needs.

Azure Blob storage was chosen for its scalability, durability, and seamless integration with cloud-based applications. It provides a reliable and cost-effective solution for storing .ows and .pkcls files, which are essential components in the AI Visual tool. Azure Blob storage ensures secure, efficient, and easily accessible file storage, supporting the AI tool's functionality while facilitating data management and access across different environments.

4.6. FastAPI

FastAPI [11] is a modern and high-performance web framework for building APIs with Python 3.8 and above. It is one of the most popular API framework due to its speed, simplicity, and automatic documentation capabilities.

One of FastAPI's key features is its asynchronous support, allowing developers to build asynchronous APIs effortlessly. This is particularly advantageous for applications that demand concurrent operations and improved responsiveness.

FastAPI emphasizes automatic OpenAPI and JSON Schema generation, making API documentation an integral part of the development process. The generated documentation is interactive, detailed, and serves as a valuable resource for both developers and API consumers.

Its intuitive design, coupled with automatic validation, serialization, and documentation, makes FastAPI a robust and efficient framework for API development.

FastAPI was adopted for its efficiency, simplicity, and speed in developing web APIs. It offers a Python-based framework that enables the creation of robust and high-performance web services for the AI Visual tool. FastAPI's automatic data validation, interactive documentation generation, and asynchronous capabilities streamline the development of the backend architecture, making it easier to handle requests and responses efficiently. This results in a faster, more responsive, and user-friendly interface for interacting with the AI Visual tool, enhancing its overall performance and usability.

4.7. API

The first version of the energy data analytics visual tool exposes a series of API to enable the upload, management and inference of Orange Data Mining pipelines. This version is designed to demonstrate the tool capabilities and therefore only implements the basic functions and runs as a stand-alone application, in the future it will be integrated with the rest of the DATA CELLAR architecture.

4.7.1. Inference Model

Name: inference

Request type: POST

Description: Inference the selected model on the given data. The model needs to be enabled to allow the inference. Some checks are performed on the selected model and on the input data to avoid errors.

Input:

- **model_id (string):** The UUID of the model to be inferenced
- **input_file (binary):** The file containing the input data in CSV format

Output:

- **output_file (binary):** The file containing the output data in CSV format resembling the Orange Data Mining output file. In case of error a message describing the error is returned instead

POST /inference Inference ⬆

Cancel
Reset

Name	Description
model_id * required string <small>(query)</small>	<input style="width: 90%;" type="text" value="1b24e1e0-f621-4f97-b4b6-16eacdd09d00"/>

Request body required multipart/form-data ▾

input_file * required
string(\$binary)

Scegli file

Execute
Clear

Responses

Curl

```
curl -X 'POST' \
'http://localhost:8081/inference?model_id=1b24e1e0-f621-4f97-b4b6-16eacdd09d00' \
-H 'accept: */*' \
-H 'Content-Type: multipart/form-data' \
-F 'input_file=@solar_test_data.csv;type=text/csv'
```

Request URL

```
http://localhost:8081/inference?model_id=1b24e1e0-f621-4f97-b4b6-16eacdd09d00
```

Server response

Code	Details
200	<p>Response body</p> <pre style="background-color: #343a40; color: #f0f0f0; padding: 10px; border: 1px solid #444;">DateTime,POWER_PRODUCTION time,continuous meta, 2020-06-14 10:00:00,1323.47 2020-06-14 11:00:00,2212.44 2020-06-14 12:00:00,3329.66 2020-06-14 13:00:00,3856.71 2020-06-14 14:00:00,5415.76 2020-06-14 15:00:00,5224.9 2020-06-14 16:00:00,5181.49 2020-06-14 17:00:00,5393.57 2020-06-14 18:00:00,5716.51 2020-06-14 19:00:00,5401.95 2020-06-14 20:00:00,5408.59 2020-06-14 21:00:00,5736.67 2020-06-14 22:00:00,5952.54 2020-06-14 23:00:00,4606.05 2020-06-15 00:00:00,2143.74 2020-06-15 01:00:00,707.897 2020-06-15 02:00:00,36.9763 2020-06-15 03:00:00,0 2020-06-15 04:00:00,0 2020-06-15 05:00:00,23.5373 2020-06-15 06:00:00,57.9652 2020-06-15 07:00:00,219.117 2020-06-15 08:00:00,540.636 2020-06-15 09:00:00,992.652 2020-06-15 10:00:00,1678.37</pre> <p>Response headers</p> <pre style="background-color: #343a40; color: #f0f0f0; padding: 10px; border: 1px solid #444;">content-length: 2525 content-type: text/csv; charset=utf-8 date: Wed, 15 Nov 2023 10:47:31 GMT etag: 45a1ced15bf40939899841edfdc83d85 last-modified: Wed, 15 Nov 2023 10:47:42 GMT server: uvicorn</pre>

Figure 4-2 Inference API, the UUID of the model is required

4.7.2. Upload Model

Name: upload

Request type: POST

Description: Upload a model on the platform. A new entry is inserted in the relational database containing the model metadata and the configuration file and the models archive's content are uploaded on the blob storage. Some checks are performed on the configuration file and on the models archive to avoid errors.

Input:

- **model_name (string):** The name of the model to be uploaded
- **model_description (string):** The description of the model to be uploaded
- **enabled (boolean):** A flag indicating whether the model is enabled for inferences or not
- **cfg_file (binary):** The Orange Data Mining inference pipeline configuration in OWS format
- **models_archive (binary):** An archive in ZIP format containing all the models' configurations and weights in PKCLS format

Output:

- **response (string):** A text containing a confirmation message and the model UUID in case of success and an error message otherwise

The screenshot shows the API configuration for the 'upload' endpoint. It includes a 'Parameters' section with the following fields:

- model_name** (string, required): consumption anomaly
- model_description** (string, required): energy consumption anomaly detection
- enabled** (boolean, required): true

The 'Request body' is set to 'multipart/form-data' and includes two file upload fields:

- cfg_file** (string(\$binary), required): prova_inference.ows
- models_archive** (string(\$binary), required): random_forest.zip

Buttons for 'Execute' and 'Clear' are located at the bottom of the interface.

Figure 4-3 upload API request, model name, model description, inference pipeline file (cfg_file) and zipped model pickle file (models_archive) are required

Code	Details
200	<p>Response body</p> <pre>{ "response": "Successfully uploaded orange inference workflow 233786e9-37a7-4022-9bb2-c8644e5270f7 to Orange Deployment Module repository" }</pre> <p>Response headers</p> <pre>content-length: 137 content-type: application/json date: Wed, 15 Nov 2023 10:42:11 GMT server: uvicorn</pre>

Figure 4-4 upload API response, if the upload is succesful the deployed model UUID is returned

4.7.3. List Models

Name: models

Request type: GET

Description: Get the models list and the associated metadata from the relational database

Input: No inputs are required for this function

Output: A list of JSON objects, each containing:

- **model_id (string):** The UUID of the model
- **model_name (string):** The name of the model
- **model_description (string):** The description of the model
- **enabled (boolean):** The flag indicating whether the model is enabled for inferences or not

Figure 4-5 models API, returns the list of deployed models with relative metadata

4.7.4. Enable Model

Name: enable

Request type: PUT

Description: Enable a model on the platform. The model metadata is updated on the relational database. If the model doesn't exist an error is thrown.

Input:

- **model_id (string):** The UUID of the model to be enabled

Output:

- **response (string):** A text containing a confirmation message in case of success and an error message otherwise

Figure 4-6 enable API, enables a model given the UUID

4.7.5. Disable Model

Name: disable

Request type: PUT

Description: Disable a model on the platform. The model metadata is updated on the relational database. If the model doesn't exist an error is thrown.

Input:

- **model_id (string):** The UUID of the model to be disabled

Output:

- **response (string):** A text containing a confirmation message in case of success and an error message otherwise

Figure 4-7 disable API, disables a deployed model given the UUID

4.7.6. Delete Model

Name: delete

Request type: DELETE

Description: Delete a model on the platform. The model metadata, the configuration file and the models archive are deleted from the relational database and the blob storage. If the model doesn't exist an error is thrown.

Input:

- **model_id (string):** The UUID of the model to be deleted

Output:

- **response (string):** A text containing a confirmation message in case of success and an error message otherwise

Figure 4-8 delete API, permanently deletes a deployed model given the UUID

5. Next steps

In the initial phase of development, The primary focus was on creating the essential functions required to enable the deployment platform to operate as a standalone service. To fully integrate the tool with the broader DATA CELLAR ecosystem, several additional steps will be necessary.

One critical step involves defining and incorporating self-descriptive information for input and output data, as well as the service itself. This is vital for publishing the service on both the Federated Catalogue and the Marketplace. Technically, this process entails including the necessary data in the database and modifying the API endpoints to retrieve this information when required. Fortunately, the architecture to accomplish this is already in place.

Another step towards integration involves user identity verification, which will be confirmed through an identity provider with each request. This ensures that individuals requesting access to the API are legitimate platform users. The same applies to the DLT-based marketplace. Beyond identity verification, communication with the marketplace will be established to confirm that users who request access to a service have made the appropriate payments (verified by blockchain transactions) and that corresponding tokens are burned when the service is used. These integrations may involve making API calls to the identity provider and marketplace endpoints.

In addition to integration efforts, there is room for enhancing the tool itself. For instance, it may be beneficial to conduct inference tests before uploading a model to ensure its proper functionality. This could require users to upload sample input and output files, a feature not included initially to maintain a streamlined focus on the core model deployment functionality.

Furthermore, improvements related to scalability are under consideration. Testing for multiple concurrent requests will be essential, and the deployment platform should be equipped to handle such scenarios. This work will align with the objectives of task 5.1, especially considering that a distinct deployment technology will be implemented for traditional AI services, but the data space will remain agnostic to this distinction.

6. Conclusion

The primary goal within Task 6.1 was to establish a versatile platform where analysts could easily create, deploy, and share advanced machine learning models to unlock the potential of energy data.

The aim was to create an ecosystem that encourages analysts to integrate cutting-edge techniques into their workflows and share their tools with fellow users. This endeavour focused on enhancing analytical capabilities across the data space, promoting informed decision-making, resource optimization, and innovation.

The data analytics visual tool is defined by its commitment to user experience, offering an intuitive interface based on Orange data mining, an Open source and well established platform that empowers both experts and non-experts to create effective data analysis pipelines.

The tool was built upon this open-source solutions, to provide a robust and user-friendly interface for designing intricate data analysis workflows. These workflows are then seamlessly uploaded to a central server via web APIs, facilitating deployment and accessibility for other DATA CELLAR users.

This tool will be fundamental to foster collaboration and promote data-driven decision making within the energy sector, as well as advance the growth of a data and service economy within DATA CELLAR stakeholders.

7. References

- [1] Janez Demšar and Blaž Zupan, Orange: Data Mining Fruitful and Fun - A Historical Perspective University of Ljubljana 2012
- [2] Orange official website <https://orangedatamining.com/>
- [3] Numpy python library <https://numpy.org/>
- [4] Scikit learn python library <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>
- [5] Orange User Interface visualization, image from Blaz Zupan, https://upload.wikimedia.org/wikipedia/commons/4/4e/Orange_data_mining%2C_visual_programming_interface%2C_May_2013.png
- [6] Orange tutorials and documentation <https://orangedatamining.com/docs/>
- [7] Orange widget development guide <https://orange-widget-base.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>
- [8] Docker official website <https://www.docker.com/>
- [9] PostgreSQL official website <https://www.postgresql.org/>
- [10] Azure Blob storage official website <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/products/storage/blobs>
- [11] FastAPI official website <https://fastapi.tiangolo.com/>